

Draft introduction to the SNF postdoctoral project

**“Gender and Nation in the Biographical Interpretations of Lesya
Ukrainka’s Life and Works: Ukraine-Russian Empire-USSR, 1898-2022”**

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Interpretation as a Historical Act:

Women's and Nationhood Issues in Lesya Ukrainka and Her Readers

*Somewhere out there, deep in history, deeply buried,
Hides a memory of her. Who is she¹ ?*

(Lesya Ukrainka, "Forgotten Shadow",
In *Thoughts and Dreams* ["Забута тінь", *Думи і мрії*, 1898])

Introduction

Main questions

At the crossroads of reception studies and women's and gender studies, this research project aims to develop a new approach of the poetic, dramatic and epistolary production of Lesya Ukrainka (real name Laryssa Kossatch-Kvitka, 1871-1913) by studying the successive readings of her work in Ukraine, the Russian Empire and the USSR. More specifically, we will focus on the representations of women in relation to the Ukrainian question in Ukrainka's work, and on the reception of these representations. Indeed, Ukrainka is one of the founding figures of literature written by women in Ukraine, and she struggled both for female and Ukrainian emancipation (she is for example very proud to be the author or the first Ukrainian and "female" version of Don Juan [*Stone Master of the House*, *Камінний господар*, 1911]). Many of her works are structured around female heroines – one thinks, for example, of *Cassandra* [*Кассандра*, 1903-1907], or *Boyar's Wife* [*Бояриня*, 1914, deleted from the complete works of Ukrainka in the USSR], and, more broadly, her female characters include Rachel, Joan of Arc, Ophelia, Niobe, etc.

More precisely, we will ask ourselves what relationship to history the readings of such a doubly peripheralized work (since it is written by a woman in a world that confines women to the peripheries of the cultural world, and by a Ukrainian woman in an Empire that has assigned Ukraine the status of border territory) can develop: are they simply influenced (by mimicry or by reaction) by the dominant representations (of Ukraine and of women, in particular), or, on the contrary, do they contribute to making history? Our guiding hypothesis will be that, since Lesya Ukrainka's work is intended to be historical by its very material (since it is a work which, by its double peripheral dimension, tends to make readable lines that are obscured by the dominant historical narratives), her readings are historically performative interpretations which, by highlighting certain aspects of the work and suppressing others, aim to make the same selection in the field of history (considered as a narrative). In this way, the reading is always redoubled, the work being considered both as an independent system requiring an internal interpretation, and as a piece of history requiring to be understood in the larger corpus of discourses that make history, or rather through the reading of which history is made.

Our main question will be divided into a series of sub-questions:

- a) Do the judgements made about Ukrainka's work depend on the image (or even the myth) of the author that critics construct, or is it the other way round? We will thus attempt to propose a typology of Lesya Ukrainka's images (as a woman and as a Little Russian/Ukrainian) and of the (literary) imaginaries that these images convey or produce.

¹ We translate: "Деся там, на дні історії, глибоко / Лежить про неї спогад. Хто вона?" (Ukrainka, 2021, vol. 5: 209)

- b) How has Ukrainka's work been categorised from a cultural point of view? Has it been perceived and/or presented as peripheral (in relation to the centralism of the Russian Empire), national, cosmopolitan/international? And what do these categorisations tell us about Ukrainka's work, its interpretative possibilities, but also the identity values claimed by the critics who studied her works?
- c) What are the values that underlie the critical judgements made about Ukrainka? In the name of what conceptions of the Ukrainian writer's duties do the traditionalist critics of his time reproach her, for example, for having preferred the "European" mythical material to the "national" folkloric material?

Corpus, approaches, state of the art

Our corpus will therefore be mainly composed of texts written by literary critics from Ukraine, the Russian Empire and the USSR, notably articles and monographs, but also letters and biographical works, insofar as the construction of the author's figure influences the interpretations of her work (for the most important milestones, see Franko (1898); Brockhaus and Efron (1890-1906); Efremov (1902); Dontcov (1922); Zerov (1924); Mouzychka (1925); Drai-Khmara (1926); Ischuk (1950); Deich (1954); Zhouravska (1963); Zadesnianskiy (1965), Zborovska (2002) and Zabuzhko (2007). We will try to show both the permanence and the metamorphosis of certain questions, beyond the great historical caesuras that were the Revolution of 1917 and the Independence of 1991. The question of cultural categorisation is central from the first period of Ukrainka's reception, with Brockhaus and Efron's *Encyclopaedic Dictionary* [ЭСБЕ, 1890-1906] criticising her for not highlighting Little Russia enough in her work: "In fact, Little Russia is little represented in Ukrainka's poetry; there is no Ukrainian nature, no Ukrainian folk life. Ukrainka connects with Little Russia, mainly, through language²." On the other hand, the inscription of her work in the context of world literature is not questioned. In the Soviet world, the categorisations will of course change radically (we will, moreover, study the disparities in this classification, for, despite a certain homogeneity, the representations of Ukrainka vary both in space and time within the Soviet world). The *Great Soviet Encyclopedia* [БСЭ, 1969-1978] will thus note: "Lesya Ukrainka, who died at the age of 42, occupied an important place in the official pantheon of classics of multinational literature in the Soviet era³." If she is appreciated, it is at the cost of reinterpreting her dual struggle for the emancipation of women and Ukraine, which, emptied of its substance, is transformed into a struggle for the liberation of the people – in such a way that she would have transformed the national drama into an international one (in the political sense of the term "international"). Finally, in post-1991 Ukraine, Lesya Ukrainka remains an icon of the national cause – hence her representation as *Notre-Dame d'Ukraine* by Zabuzhko (2007).

With regard to the more specifically situated question of the way in which femininity was and is thought of in Ukraine and the Soviet world, we will draw on the following studies.

First of all, we will of course use the critical references of the last thirty years on Lesya Ukrainka in particular on *Symposium* (2021); *Proceedings* (1983); Wedel (1991); Banatska (2000); Lajoie and Lajoie (2001); Zborovska (2002); Krys (2007); Zabuzhko (2007); Hundorova (2009); Hundorova (2011); Sikora (2012); Levtchenko (2013); Podlisetska (2017) (as these references constitute an important part of our corpus of study, we will discuss them at greater length below).

² We translate: "Собственно Малороссия в поэзии Л. представлена мало; нет ни украинской природы, ни украинского народного быта. С Малороссией Л. связывает, главным образом, язык."

³ We translate: "Скончавшаяся в возрасте 42 лет Леся Украинка в советское время занимала видное место в официальном пантеоне классиков многонациональной литературы."

Insofar as the issues of women's emancipation and national emancipation are intimately linked for both Ukrainka and her post-1991 readers, we will place our research in the context of post-imperial studies and think about the question of writing history and (gendered or national) identity in relation to the question of the relationship between centre and periphery: see, among others, Geyer (1987); Saïd (1993); Layton (1994); Geraci (2001); Thompson (2002); Ram (2003); Laruelle (2005); Tolz (2005, 2011); Cadiot (2007); Etkind (2011); Elam (2021).

As our approach to Ukrainka's work and its readings is intended to be historically contextualised, we will also draw on studies of women's rights and fights in Russian Empire, in late 19th-century Ukraine and in the USSR. We will refer (among others) to Bohachevsky-Chomiak (1988), Roudnitska (1998), Kay (2000), Hrycak (2002), Pavlychko (2002), Peto (2004), Miroiu (2007), Zirin *et al.* (2007), Robertson (2011), Studer (2015).

Furthermore, studies on women's *corpora* and on the political and social role of women in the Soviet, post-Soviet and Ukrainian worlds constitute a rapidly expanding field. We will refer to the following studies: on the reception of women, gender and queer studies in Ukraine, Zborovska (1999), Kis (2013), but also Einhorn (1993); on the popularisation of feminism in Ukraine, Rubchak (2001), Martceniouk (2018), Popova (2016), Mayerchyk (2019); on feminism in the post-USSR world, on the success of gender studies and on the subsequent "birth of a field" in the countries of the former USSR, Graff (2003), Kichorovska Kebalo (2007), Daskalova (2010, 2011, 2012), Tlostanova (2010, 2011), Mlinarevic *et al.* (2010, 2011), Solovey (2018); for exemplary studies of what women's and gender studies in Ukraine are in the literary field, Rubchak (1996, 2001, 2009, 2012), Ageeva (1999, 2001, 2003, 2008, 2019), Hundorova (1991, 2002, 2011, 2017), Pavlychko (1992, 2002, 2008), Chuhim (2006), without forgetting the trilingual Ukrainian-Russian-English journal *Feminist Critique: East European Journal of Feminist and Queer Studies*, Online: <https://feminist.krytyka.com/en/issues/feminist-critique-4-2021>; for an overview of Ukrainian women's studies in the field of sociological/political studies, Lavrynenko (1999), Oksamytna (2005, 2001), and Kis (2005, 2007, 2012, 2013, 2015); in the historical field, Smoliar (1998, 1999), and Malanchuk-Rybak (1999, 2002, 2006, 2008); on the relationship between feminism and nationalism, Pavlychko (1992, 1997, 2008), Zborovska (1999), Yuval-Davis (1996), Shkandrij (2001), Zhurzhenko (2001, 2008, 2011), Plahotnik (2011), Mayerchyk (2019).

Finally, in order to better understand the role of the figure of Lesya Ukrainka in women's action in relation to the major events in Ukraine's recent history, we will draw, among others, on the following studies: on the actions of Femen, Maiierchyk and Plahotnik, 2010; Channell, 2014; and O'Keefe, 2014); on the Orange revolution, Hrycak, 2007; on the Maïdan (which has been seen as a "women's affair"), Virtosu, 2014, Phillips, 2014, Khromeychuk, 2015, Martsenyuk, 2014; on the myths that underlie the political action of certain women, such as Tymoshenko (whose visual communication is based on codes borrowed from the iconography of Ukrainka), Rubchak, 2001, 2012, and Kis, 2005, 2007.

Why the project is innovative

This project is fundamentally innovative because:

1) Ukrainian studies are still almost non-existent in France today, regardless of the discipline (history, Slavonic studies or comparative literature). One of the reasons for this black hole is the lack of academic positions in Ukrainian Studies, even within the Slavic Studies section: for example, there is only one position of lecturer in Ukrainian Studies at INALCO in Paris. In Switzerland, Ukrainian Studies is more developed – the host institute being an absolutely crucial institution in this field – but it is still a largely underdeveloped field.

2) Literary studies on the history of Ukrainian women's thought (*i.e.* both the history of women writers and intellectuals and the history of women's thought) are even less developed, whether in France or more broadly in Europe (one of the major exceptions being the work of the supervisor – see Aust & Schenk, 2015, 2020; Schenk, 2013, 2017, 2020); yet this is a vast and crucial body of work that constitutes an important source of knowledge and analytical tools that it would be inappropriate to ignore. The writings of Ukrainian women suffer from a lack of visibility or readability due to the fact that women authors are still in a minority in the country (and perhaps in the whole world), and that Ukrainian literature is little translated and little taught, especially in France (in Italy, Canada and the United States, the Ukrainian diaspora is more present, and the Ukrainian studies are more developed).

3) Finally, this project will make it possible to disseminate in France gender studies practices specific to post-1991 Ukraine (see Zhurzhenko, 2010), and to make known an alternative history of feminism, which does not respect the “waves” system specific to French and American feminism, but seeks tutelary figures in Ukrainian women writers of the turn of the twentieth century, one of the most important of whom is Ukrainka.

It should also be noted that this project, whose one of the major objects of study is the strategies of censorship and emancipation at work in the acts of reading and interpretation, is directly related to the struggle that women and feminists are waging today to avoid, in the context of the Ukrainian war, the return in force of cultural and gendered assignments.

Presentation of the plan

Our project will develop along two lines:

1) First, we will ask how, and at the cost of what reinventions (censorship of certain aspects of her work, distortion of its ideological content, etc.), Ukrainka's work has been categorized. We will organise our approach around three complex but homogeneous periods: the immediate reception, during the author's lifetime and up to 1917, the “Soviet” reception, and finally, the post-independence Ukrainian reception.

2) Then, we will then ask how the “feminism” of Ukrainka's texts has evolved over time, and attempt to rethink her work from the (cultural and ideological) gap between the author's own vision of women in literature and its later reinterpretations (especially those that use the tools of women's and gender studies).

I. Little Russian? Ukrainian? Global? Feminine? Categorisations of Ukrainka's work

We will therefore first try to analyse both the way in which Ukrainka wanted to situate her work in world literature, and how successive critics have interpreted (or ignored) this desire. The question is directly related to the perception (or not) of Ukrainka as a woman writer – for, during her lifetime, she had to suffer from prejudices that denied her, as a woman, access to the canon of world literature. We will divide this axis into three parts, organised according to a historical logic.

1) A double peripheralisation? The reception of Ukrainka until 1917

This first reception leads us to ask ourselves several questions:

a) Is Ukrainka perceived and portrayed as a Ukrainian writer, or is her work captured in a wider literary and cultural context? At first glance, it seems that Ukrainka is primarily unappreciated for the desire for identity emancipation through openness to the world that manifests itself in the European intertext that structures her work (even though the actors of the

second “national revival” in the early nineteenth century tried to adapt the values of the European Enlightenment to the reality of their country in the context of Russian imperialism – see Pavlyshyn, 2010, 188).

She is guided in this by her uncle exiled in Geneva, who is none other than Mykhailo Drahomanov, specialist of classical antiquity, whose stay in Europe (in Berlin, Prague, Vienna, Florence, Heidelberg, etc.) in the 1870s gave him enough perspective to get an overview of European literature (see Zhouravska, 1963), and to develop a comparative approach to the literature of Ukraine (see for example his 1874 lecture on the “Slavic Treatment of Œdipal History” [“Слов’янські переробки Едіпової історії”]), and his comparisons of Ukrainian written and oral literature with Slovak literature and with literatures of North Asia and the Caucasus (*Between West and East. Comparative Essays on Ukrainian Folk Literature* [Між Заходом і Сходом. Порівняльні нариси української народної словесності]). Ukrainka thus wishes to place her work in the context of world literature (on world literature, see Casanova, 1999; Damrosch, 2003; Nalyvaiko, 2007). Indeed, in her work in literary criticism, she has more than once adopted a comparative perspective within the intellectual framework drawn by the notion of *Weltliteratur* (in 1900, for example, she published an article entitled “The Little Russian Writers of Bucovina” [Малорусские писатели на Буковине], where she compared the works of Olha Kobylanska (1863-1942), the German writer Gabriele Reuter (1859-1941) and the Italian Neera – real name Anna Radius Zuccari (1846-1918), author of *Teresa*, 1886; and in another article, entitled “New Perspectives and Old Shadows. “The New Woman” of Western European Letters⁴” [Новые перспективы и старые тени. “Новая женщина” западноевропейской беллетристики, 1900], she studied the social representations of women in the literature of France, Germany, England and the northern countries). In addition, she questioned the emergence of “minor” literatures, which are characterised by their limited territorial scope:

In our time, with the colossal development of the so-called “world literatures”, an interesting phenomenon is perceived: the literatures of small peoples, and even of small ethnographic groups, are beginning to raise their voices, more and more loudly, and with more and more confidence, defending their “minority right⁵”. (Ukrainka, 2021, vol. 7: 97)

She is also an irreplaceable cultural mediator in the history of Ukrainian literature. She translated Homer, Victor Hugo, Adam Mickiewicz and Heinrich Heine (but also – because her curiosity did not stop at Europe – the *Rig-Veda* – not forgetting that she also wrote an *Ancient History of the Eastern Peoples* [Стародавня історія східних народів, 1918]). If this aspect of her work is little appreciated by Ukrainian and even Ukrainianophile critics, it is because Ukrainka claims to embody what in Ukraine is called modernism – a modernism that her “traditionalist” readers consider to be anti-popular, and which they fear will shake the patriarchy to its foundations.

b) The second question is the following: is Ukrainka perceived as a typically female writer? At first glance, it seems to us that the reaction we have just described is not accompanied by any real reflection on “women’s literature”, which does not yet seem to have become an object of reflection for male and/or traditionalist critics. However, Ukrainka raises the question of a possible specificity of women’s literature, even if she rejects the hypothesis of a typically female literature. Indeed, she believes that female “separatism” is harmful, and that the texts it

⁴ In the corpus treated in this article, English, French, German, Italian, Scandinavian, Polish, Russian and Ukrainian literature are represented.

⁵ We translate: “В наше время на ряду с колоссальным развитием так называемых ‘мировых’ литератур замечается одно интересное явление; литературы маленьких народов, даже небольших этнографических групп, начинают все гроче и увереннее поднимать голос, защищая свое ‘право меньшинства’.”

produces are “boring⁶” (Letter to M. Dragomanov dated 1893, *Ukrainka*, 2021, vol. 11: 208) (this is what she reproaches the Galician feminist Natalia Kobrynska, who in 1887, together with Olena Pchilka, founded the journal *First Crown: the Women’s Almanac* [*Перший вінок: жіночий альманах*], which did not survive its first issue, but is nevertheless a fundamental publication in the history of theories of the feminine in Ukraine, insofar as Kobrynska compares, in an article entitled “About the Women’s Movement in Modern Times” [“Про рух жіночий новіших часах”], the state of the women’s question in the United States and in Western European countries). For *Ukrainka* (and she shared this conviction with other women writers of the time, such as Olha Kobylanska or Natalia Kobrynska, with whom she participated in the creation of the “Ukrainian Girls’ Circle” and the “Women’s Society”, women must make their place in literature through the value of their works, but their aim should not be to be understood as a singular category of writers. She therefore appreciates that most critics of her time do not treat her as a woman writer – and regrets that in Galicia, a certain feminist movement is trying to impose criticism of women’s works as a speciality: “Our critics are not such knights, [...] they put poets, poetesses, literators and women writers on the same level; [...] more than once I have thanked them for it⁷.” [Letter to O. Makovei dated 28 January 1894. *Ibid.*: 271] Moreover, she bases her argument on a precedent that she borrows from the West, since she would like to reproduce the critical and theoretical strategies of women writers in England: “it is such a narrow river, these women’s publications. When a being is already destined not to swim [amply], one should not deprive him of what remains of his will. I think that it is not after swimming in such rivers that English women have had access to the sea⁸.” [Letter to M. Pavlyk dated 11-12 March 1895. *Ibid.*: 359] However, while the question of a possible specificity of women’s writing is not often addressed by Ukrainian critics (of which *Ukrainka* therefore considers Galician critics not to be a part), on the other hand, *Ukrainka* is treated as a woman, *i.e.*, as a being capable of writing literature like men, but without ever really equalling them. She does not want to be identified either as a “Little Russian” or as a “little woman”, and is too often reduced to the status of a “little girl” by critics. The writer Ivan Franko, in particular, falls into this trap, even though he is in favour of the cultural and artistic emancipation of women (he studied the works of John Stuart Mill and his wife Harriet Taylor Mill – including *The Subjection of Women*, 1869). In “Female subjection in Rus’ folk songs” [“Жіноча неволя в руських піснях народних”, 1883], he described the female struggle as it develops through this folklore, which he compares sometimes to Russian folklore, sometimes to Polish, sometimes to Hungarian; and he also emphasised that the social and family subjugation of Ukrainian women is inseparable from their lack of openness to the foreign world, especially the West (on his “feminism”, see Gossovskaya, 2013). In an article dedicated to *Ukrainka*, which she later criticised as phallogocentric in her correspondence, Franko (1898) implied that she practised a primitive and non-popular style of writing (this was a commonplace in the criticism of her work at the time, with *Ukrainka* being reproached for preferring the European mythical material to the national traditional one). As a result, Franko describes her poems as childish (or “childish-naïve”, to be precise – Franko, 1898: 9). He compares her to Shevchenko – who embodies a kind of ideal of the Ukrainian and traditionalist writer, and who fulfils the type of the bard, the singer of the nation – but without considering her as his equal:

⁶ We translate: “Не скучно хіба, коли описуються факти з жіночого життя і розбирається жіноча психологія у гарній формі та ще й з таланом, і то сепаратизм трохи смішноватий.”

⁷ We translate: “Видно, справді, у вас в Галичині ‘жіноче питання’ дуже в моді тепер, бо Ви раз у раз на його звертаєте. Навіть вибрали собі спеціальність ‘критика дівочих творів’, – не можна сказати, щоб се була дуже широка спеціальність... От наші критики не такі лицарі, і коли приходиться до діла, то ставлять в одну лінію і поетів, і поетес, і літератів, і літераток; не знаю, як хто, а я не раз казала їм за спасибі. А рггос жіночої літератури, – де треба вдаватись тому, хто хоче спровадити собі ‘Нашу Долю’, чи треба вдаватись до самої п. Кобр[инської]? Я б написала дещо Вам з поводу ‘жіночої літ[ератури]’, але нехай потім, се довга річ, а я довго не можу писати.”

⁸ We translate: “така се вже вузенька річечка, сі жіночі видання. Коли ж кому і так судилось не глибоко та не широко плавати, то не хочеться позбавляти себе остатньої волі. Я гадаю, що англічанки не такими річками виплили в море.”

this is again a *topos* of the criticism of the time on Ukrainka, her dramas being considered as the manifestation of a true literary genius, but her poetry being considered mediocre, so that the comparison with Shevchenko always turns to her disadvantage. Franko's conclusion, which is meant to be eulogistic, concentrates all the contradictions of this male criticism which greets with a benevolence tinged with condescension the birth of a literature made by women: "I repeat once again: when you read the soft and nervous or coldly resonant writings of young modern Ukrainian men and compare them with these joyful, strong and courageous, and at the same time so simple and sincere words of Lesya Oukrainka, you involuntarily think that this ill girl, this weak girl, is almost a unique man for the whole of modern Ukraine⁹." Certainly, Franko goes as far as he could go – even seeming to prefigure gender theory in some respects, as he distinguishes symbolic sex from physical sex. But he still stages Ukrainka's physical weakness (she was a tuberculosis patient), in accordance with a developing myth, which makes her the embodiment of a courageous but incurably ill Ukraine. She responded to this myth in a poem entitled "Who Told You I Was Weak?" (1911) (Ukrainka, 2021, vol. 5: 423):

*Who told you I was weak,
That I was giving in to fate?
Is my hand shaking,
Is my singing and thinking ill¹⁰?*

Thus, in the first phase of this history of critical readings of Ukrainka, we observe a redoubling of peripheralisation: the critics who deal with her work are mostly Ukrainian traditionalists, who are themselves considered "peripheral" in a centralist Russian Empire; but these traditionalists reproduce this same gesture, and, considering themselves central to Ukrainian culture, condemn the literature produced by this woman, who is not very radical in her "feminist" stances and yet highly concerned with the national cause (her pseudonym proves it), to remain on the periphery of the cultural canon.

2) Ukrainka, a writer fighting for emancipation – but from what? The Soviet Era

The sub-heading above asks the main question of the second major period we are interested in: the Soviet era. Of course, this era can be divided into several sub-periods in terms of the readings and interpretations of Ukrainka's work, but it seems to us to be very homogeneous from the point of view of the gestures of reading and interpretation that are imposed on the writer's texts. There are two gestures in particular that are almost systematically found: suppression (of certain passages of the works in their Soviet editions and in their critical readings, of certain elements of the author's life in texts evoking her life); recontextualising interpretation (when the national or even feminine aspects of her emancipatory poems are ignored in order to divert the discourse of liberation in favour of the revolutionary and Bolshevik cause).

In 1950, a biography of Ukraïnka (Ischuk) was published in Kyiv. This book, although written in Ukrainian, is a particularly good example of the critical discourse on the author that had crystallised in the USSR over the previous decades. This critical discourse raises the following questions:

a) Is Ukrainka still a Ukrainian author? The exclusion of Ukrainian language and culture from Ukrainka's biography is noticeable: she was a polyglot, spoke Russian, French, English,

⁹ We translate: "Ще раз повторюю : читаючи м'які та рознервовані, або холодно резонерські писання сучасних молодих Українців мужчин і порівнюючи їх з тими бадьорими, сильними та сьмілими, а при тім такими простими, такими щирими словами Лесі Українки, ми моволі думаєш, що ся хора, слабосила дівчина — трохи чи не одинокий мужчина на всю новочасну соборну Україну."

¹⁰ We translate: "Хто вам сказав, що я слабка, / що я корюся долі? / Хіба тремтить моя рука / чи пісня й думка кволі?"

German – but Ukrainian is not mentioned. Similarly, through her family environment, she would have had access to folk tales and, more broadly, to the folklore of Poland, not of Ukraine. This act of censorship is all the more worthy of study as it is part of the continuity of another, which Ukrainka had to suffer during her lifetime: the Ems Ukase (1876 – see Remy, 2017), which, even after a first relaxation in 1881 and a lifting of the restrictions in 1905, was to remain a sword of Damocles for the actors of Ukrainian and Ukrainian-speaking culture, since the restrictions were to be restored in 1910. This linguistic question cannot be avoided in a study of a woman author from the turn of the 20th century and her reception in the Soviet context. It even becomes a collective cause for women in Ukraine in the early 20th century. The founding text of the Union for Women's Equality, created in Poltava in 1905, explicitly states this: "The fate of Ukrainian women, in addition to the general, bitter and painful aspects of the women's question, is strongly influenced by the difficult circumstances resulting from the oppression of the Ukrainian people. [...] Language – the only means of expressing thoughts – since those times when Ukraine lost its political independence after the Treaty of Pereyaslav, has been developed only by individual workers, and their works often could not see the light of day in their own homeland, or appeared only several years after their completion¹¹."

b) The second question is more broadly theoretical: what distinguishes a reinterpretation from an overinterpretation or a misinterpretation? Indeed, Soviet interpretations of Ukrainka's commitment are largely abusive – and so one would have to define the system of interpretive values by which an interpretation can be designated as abusive. In any case, Ukrainka's rejection of pure art is interpreted as a sure sign of revolutionary commitment: her entire creative work is thus associated with the revolutionary movement of the late 19th and early 20th centuries. According to the dominant reading in the Soviet world, Lesya Ukrainka was deeply aware of the social function of the artistic word, and was actively involved in the socio-political struggle, to the point of being, in her poetry, a real figurehead of the proletarian revolution. As for her real participation in the struggle for the interests of Ukraine, against the marginalising gestures of the Russian Empire, it is emptied of its content, and interpreted as a struggle for the fundamental interests of the exploited and oppressed peoples, as a fight against their oppressive tyrants, as a propaganda work for liberating ideas, starting with those of scientific socialism. In particular, lines like the following are over-interpreted by means of abusive recontextualisation and re-ideologisation:

*He is not a poet who forgets
Terrible wounds of the people,
To put on your hands free
Even golden chains¹²! (Ancient Tale [Давня Казка, 1893]; Ukrainka, 2021, vol. 5 : 507])*

We can also quote the critic Mouzychka (1965), who compares Ukrainka's poem *Cassandra* to an "Iliad of the Ukrainian people" (it is the noun "people", not the adjective "Ukrainian" that counts here), adding this comment: "The Russian tsarist government is like the Achaeans who besieged Troy. [...] The proletariat is increasingly threatening its economic demands and at the

¹¹ *New Community [Нова Громада]*, n° 1, 1906, p. 131. We translate: "На долю жінок українок, окрім загальних гірких та болючих сторін жіночого питання мають, значний вплив і ті тяжкі обставини, що виходять з пригнічування українського народу. [...] Мову – цей єдиний спосіб до вислову думок – з того часу, як Україна, після переяславської умови, втратила політичну самостійність, – розвивали тільки поодинокі робітники, і їх твори часто не могли побачити світу в рідній країні, або з'являлися через довгі роки після того, як їх викінчено."

¹² We translate: "Не поет, хто забуває / Про страшні народні рани, / Щоб собі на вільні руки / Золоті надіть кайдани!"

same time beginning to prepare to wrest state power from the hands of the nobility. The struggle of the Achaeans with the Trojans for the beautiful Helena (power) is already evident¹³.”

c) Another fundamental feature of Lesya Ukrainka's Soviet readings is their extremely virulent criticism of the readings that preceded them. Hence this theoretical question: is a reinterpretation necessarily constructed against the interpretations that preceded it, or is it the prerogative of ideologically committed interpretations? In any case, Soviet critics claim that contemporary bourgeois nationalist critics have “obscured” the “revolutionary essence” of Ukrainka's work and grossly distorted the ideological content of some of her most remarkable works, especially her dramas and dramatic poems. Even after her death, moreover, Ukrainka was reportedly the victim of indelicate critics: “nationalists, low-grade sociologists and rootless cosmopolitans” tried in every way to devalue her actions for the good of the people, tried to uproot her from the people's soil, excluded her from the history of the Russian liberation movement, and misleadingly portrayed her as a “loner” and a tragically impotent figure. In short, her contempt for the Empire and the Tsars, the atheism of her family and the fact that she does not glorify the peasantry in her work are interpreted as clear signs of her adherence to what will become the state ideology of the USSR.

In short, this is a period of the reception and interpretation of Ukrainka's works that creates confusion – particularly in her texts, which, published in censored versions, will be published in a full and unabridged version only in 2021. However, it is very important, while underlining the overall homogeneity of critical gestures in the Soviet period, not to treat this period as a monolithic block. As early as 1965, Ukrainian critics pointed out that the interventions made to the texts made them very uncertain, and allowed for all sorts of abusive interpretations: “It is also worth noting the ‘fluidity’ and uncertainty of the text of L. Ukrainka's works in the new editions, which, together with the comments and articles of ‘literary critics’, allows their character to be fundamentally changed in the direction desired by Moscow. All the above forces us to be extremely cautious in using texts from Soviet publications and to resolutely reject ‘explanations’, ‘critical remarks’ and ‘prefaces’¹⁴.” (Zadesnianskiy, 1965)

3) Ukrainka, a woman who finally has the right to speak? 1991-2002

The third and final major period (for the time being) is the one that arose with the independence of Ukraine in 1991. Did this period finally give credence or value to Ukrainka's word as a woman? This is the question we will ask.

Among the figures that post-1991 researchers and feminists have held up as models, Ukrainka stands out for the extent of its influence. As soon as Ukraine became independent, researchers such as Hundorova, Pavlychko and Ageeva turned to Ukrainka to rethink their own practices of women's studies and to propose a version of it that was not purely modelled on Western patterns and that was consistent with the specific concerns of Ukrainian women.

The first step, of course, was to discover the critical American and European currents of gender studies and women's studies. Pavlychko was the first to open the window on Western gender studies and, together with Hundorova and Ageeva, she created the “feminist seminar” at the Kyiv Institute of Literature. What interested them was how feminism changes the way

¹³ We translate : “Пролетаріат дедалі все грізніше ставить свої економічні домагання та заразом починає розуміти зв'язок між політичною й економічною боротьбою, починає готуватися вихопити державну владу з рук дворянства. Стає ясною вже боротьба ахейців із троянцями за гарну Гелену (владу) »

¹⁴We translate : “Рівно ж мусимо відмітити ‘плинність’ і непевність тексту творів Л. Українки в нових виданнях, яка в парі з коментарями та статтями ‘літературознавців’ дає змогу ґрунтовно міняти їх характер в бажаному для Москви напрямі. [...] Все попереду сказане зобов'язує нас до надзвичайної обережності при користуванні текстами советських видань і рішучого неприймання ‘пояснення’ і ‘критичних уваг’ та ‘передмов’”.

literature is viewed, how feminist reading gives new depth to texts, whether by men or women, and how the emergence of female voices changes the Ukrainian cultural symphony. Ukrainka's work precisely thematises the stifling of women's voices and the strategies for overcoming it and triumphing over oppression: in *Catacombs* [*В катакомбах*, 1906], the character of the bishop silences the women with an unappealable formula coupled with an argument of authority legitimizing by the divine the omnipotence of men in the field of discourse (“Shut up! Our great apostle commanded: / ‘Let the woman in the congregation be silent¹⁵’” (Ukrainka, 2021, vol. 1: 241); and in *The Possessed* [*Одержима*, 1902], Ukrainka features a woman who, having no words to speak, sings to make her voice heard nonetheless (“One can sing it, but to say it – there are not enough words¹⁶” – *Ibid.*: 124).

In this perspective, the readings of Ukrainka developed by contemporary Ukrainian feminists allowed them to develop their own stream of women and gender studies. Indeed, Ukrainka and her friend Kobylanska (author of a text entitled “On the idea of the women's movement” [“Що про ідею жіночого руху”, 1894], but also of several stories with female heroines, including *She Got Married* [*Вона вийшла заміж*, 1886-1887], *The Tsar's Daughter* [*Царівна*, 1896], or *A Woman Without Culture* [*Некультурна*, 1897]) proposed to deconstruct the traditional ideal created by Ukrainian authors such as Kvitka-Osnovianenko, Kulish, Nechui-Levitskii, or Tchevchenko (even though the latter, in particular, has advanced the women's cause in Ukrainian culture by creating characters of Ukrainian women who no longer embody a legitimate and silent maternity, but are the main actors of an educational discourse aimed at making the Ukrainian language and culture audible). Pavlychko proposed a *queer* reading of the correspondence between Ukrainka and Kobylanska that emphasised the fundamental estrangement of the female values they developed, in the context of the dominant value system of the time. At first, this reading was booed by scholars, to the point that some refused to work on this Ukrainka tainted by these new interpretations: these scholars remained for a while dependent on ideological constructs haunting their bodies and souls (see Foucault, *Discipline and Punish*, 1975), before accepting, for some at least, to see in the hypotheses of feminist scholars primordial avenues to be explored. However, it is arguable that Ukrainka has come to have a feminine voice in Ukrainian academia, as, in 2021, on the occasion of the 150th anniversary of her birth (1871-1913), numerous cultural events were organised in Ukraine, and most importantly, her complete uncensored works were reissued in 14 volumes. A cultural project entitled “The 150 Names of Lesya” was also created to show that this emblematic writer of the turn of the 20th century also embodies the contemporary era (Online: <https://150imenlesi.org/>). The idea of the project is to discover, but also to identify the author without (misogynistic) stereotypes, to rid the reading of her texts of imperialist/Soviet censorship mechanisms.

However, despite the fact that feminist (and even queer) readings of Ukrainka were initially rejected outright by “traditionalist” critics, it is important to underline that the “women's question” is not addressed in a homogeneous way by all the critics who have recently dealt with Ukrainka – which also raises the question of the internal coherence of the notions of women's studies and gender studies, especially when the interpretive tools constructed by these currents, which developed between North America and Western Europe, are applied to works that are part of a very different history of mentalities.

Some critics therefore approach Ukrainka's intimate discourse, especially in her letters to Olga Kobylanska (which raises the question of whether or not the correspondence is part of the work), as a queer discourse (*i.e.* as a verbal practice of non-traditional sexuality) that participates in the struggle against traditionalism (see in particular Pavlychko, 1997). Nila Zborovska, on the other hand, develops a mytho-biographical interpretation and points out that

¹⁵ We translate: “Вмовкни! Великий наш апостол заповідав: / 'А жінка серед збору хай мовчить”

¹⁶ We translate: “Про се співати можна, а сказати – слів не стає.”

Lesya Ukrainka “ruthlessly rejected the Christian patriarchal myth of the apostle Paul” (Zborovska, 2002). For her part, Vera Ageeva, in a section of her essay entitled *Women’s Space: The Feminist Discourse of Ukrainian Modernism* (2003), takes an exclusively feminist approach to the writer’s work. And Oksana Zabuzhko, playing on the transfer between symbolic and physical sex, describes Ukrainka as a “noble knight” (Zabuzhko, 2007). Finally, Tamara Hundorova focuses on the problem of “women’s communication” and “the singularity of womens’ writing” (Hundorova, 2009: 422).

In addition, it is worth asking whether this post-1991 period should not be split in two, and whether there is not a before and after 2014. Indeed, as Bénédicte Santoire (2022) reminds us: “In every war, the resulting humanitarian crisis deepens and aggravates the inequities of the patriarchal system”, and in this context, it is possible that the readings of Ukrainka have evolved in concert with the evolution of the modalities of female action in Ukraine.

The actions of Femen (see Maierchyk and Plahotnik, 2010; Channell, 2014; and O’Keefe, 2014) had already been read in the light of the precedent set, in a completely different register, by Ukrainka’s struggles for women. Let’s take the example of Inna Shevchenko, who, in her book entitled *Heroic Women. Amazons, sinners, revolutionaries*, shows that feminist activism have long been frowned upon in Ukraine, both by men, women and other feminists (see also Reestorff, 2014), and is sometimes still seen through the prism of Soviet moral rules. The same Inna Shevchenko declares that “among [the] Ukrainian feminist intellectuals, Lesya Ukrainka is one of [her] icons”; and in her next book, *First name: Inna* (2021) she evokes the “revolutionary feminism of Lesya Ukrainka”.

But what kind of revolution are we talking about? Since 2014, shouldn’t we be talking about women at war? In fact, each of the major events that have marked the recent history of Ukraine has, together with the evolution of the media context, contributed to reshaping the possibilities open to women’s discourse, in relation to the work of liberating national identity – an unfinished process that has so far seen a succession of founding events such as the Orange Revolution (see Hrycak, 2007), the Maidan, which has been seen as a “women’s affair” (see Virtosu, 2014; Phillips, 2014; Khromeychuk, 2015; Martsenyuk, 2014); Russia’s Annexation of Crimea; the Donbass War; and most recently the Russian army’s general intervention in Ukraine.

This sequence of events and the role that certain women decided to play in them led to a change in the imagination and imagery of women – and Ukrainka has repeatedly served as an icon in this context. The regular use of Ukrainka’s image in photomontages that present her as a modern-day woman fighter is noticeable, especially in online projects that emerged in the context of the events leading up to Euromaidan: *Povaha* (“Respect” in Ukrainian), an anti-sexism campaign that aims to combat gender inequality and highlight women as figures in history (Online: <https://povaha.org.ua/>); the *The devochki* (“Girls” in Russian) project, that was created in 2013 in order to provide a platform for women who want to make their speech a public fact, and was renamed *divoche media* (“Media for girls” in Ukrainian) after the outbreak of the general war in Ukraine (Online: https://www.divoche.media/page/68/?no_redirect=true); and the *Gender in detail* project (Online: <https://genderindetail.org.ua/>), which was created in 2016, and focuses on the relationship between politics and feminism, from a half-academic, half-general public perspective.

Thus, it is the role of the figure of Ukrainka in the development of the imaginary of the woman as a warrior (and not as a victim – on this last *topos*, see Bucur, 2008; and Kis, 2015) that will interest us: while Nobel laureate Svetlana Aleksievich (born in Stanislav, now Ivano-Frankivsk) defends the idea that war (at least World War II) does not have a woman’s face (see Aleksievich, 1985), as of 2014, women had joined the Ukrainian military forces, and as of 2018 the right of women to enter the army is enshrined in Ukrainian law. Indeed, the war appears to be a *casus belli* for feminists, with recent work (see Plahotnik, 2011; and Mayerchyk, 2019) claiming that feminists in Ukraine can be divided into two categories: 1) post-colonial, whose

aim would be to stop the war; 2) nationalist, whose aim would be to win the war (and it would seem that feminist discourse has, as early as the 1990s, more resonance when it is in line with nationalist discourse – see Popova, 2016; and Yuval-Davis, 1996). We will therefore study the use of the image and work of Ukrainka by representatives of these two trends.

More broadly speaking, the revival of certain myths (see Rubchak, 2001 and Kis, 2005) such as that of the Beregyna, the female protector, has played a major role in the legitimisation of some female politicians: Tymoshenko, for example, has exploited the image of the Beregyna in her political strategy (see Kis, 2007), which is based on a double opposition (to the ruling power and to male hegemony in the political field – see Rubchak, 2012). This image was largely inspired by the mythification of Lesya Ukrainka as protector or even patroness saint of Ukraine – one thinks in particular of Oksana Zabushko's book, *Notre-Dame d'Ukraine: Ukrainka in the Conflict of Mythologies* (2007).

Don't these re-appropriations of the figure of Ukrainka change the way we read her works? These are one of the major questions we would like to ask: insofar as our work deals with the successive updating of Ukrainka's work through reading and interpretation, it seems essential to us to also question its relevance in 2022.

To sum up, the main question posed by most of the readings we briefly described, or at least by those of the Soviet era and those of the last thirty years, is that of the ideological interpretation of texts. Although she fought for women and for the emancipation of Ukraine, Ukrainka did not consider literature to be a matter of ideas (and even less of ideologies): her ideas are never systematically exposed, they are inserted in the body of (mostly fictional) texts where they do not play a dominant role. What we would like to study, therefore, is the way in which this refusal of ideological systematisation turns against itself, so to speak, when critics take advantage of the margin of interpretative uncertainty that this creates to appropriate the work by emphasising the ideas to the detriment of the non-ideological substratum, and then sometimes radically distorting the ideas. So where is the line between a creative interpretation that makes the work a source of inspiration for new struggles that will necessarily be very different, since the context is no longer the same, but that do not go against the author's values, and abusive reinterpretations that go against everything the author believed in? Our hypothesis is that one of the distinguishing features of creative but not abusive interpretations is that they question their own legitimacy by confronting the author's own interpretations of her own work.

II. Ukrainka, feminist in spite of herself?

The second major part of our reflection will therefore focus on the following question: to what extent do the interpretations that think of Ukrainka from the point of view of her condition as a woman (particularly in the Ukrainian world after 1991) “betray” Ukrainka's own conception of the role of femininity in literature? And how does this discrepancy (assumed or not, depending on the reading) help us to understand what makes this work movable from one era to another – and therefore perennial, and destined for a long life?

Indeed, the recent readings and interpretations of Ukrainka's work raise a major question: is it not a fundamentally post-modern gesture to read Ukrainka as a woman-author, when she herself refused to enter this category, which she rejected (but perhaps for circumstantial and strategic reasons) as irrelevant?

But precisely, it seems to us that what brings these post-1991 approaches together, apart from the question of women, is that (for the most part at least) they themselves question their own legitimacy, insofar as Lesya Ukrainka fought to place women at the heart of cultural and social life, but without ever wanting to make feminism a value in itself. Furthermore, several

of them raise the question of modernism as a rejection of traditionalism and of the legitimacy of a comparison between Ukrainka's situation in relation to the dominant discourses of the time and the situation of women researchers and writers in Ukraine in the early years after the fall of the USSR. Finally, most of these critics explore Ukrainka's dual struggle for emancipation – for women and for the Ukrainian nation to emerge from its subjugation to the Empire – with the stated aim of rethinking (but without falling into the trap of abusive assimilation) their own struggle for women in the context of Ukraine's rebirth as an independent nation after the fall of the Soviet Empire (on this topic, see Kichorovska Kebalo, 2007).

This question of ruptures and continuities between Ukrainka's own idea of the role of femininity in her own writing and the “*a posteriori* readings” of her works that have been made based on the “women's question” will be addressed through several sub-problems.

1) *Resurgence of the women's question in the readings of Ukrainka's works*

First of all, there is the question of how the question of women, which was present, albeit in a depreciatory way, in the first critical phase and then largely ignored during the Soviet era, has resurfaced to become dominant since 1991. In other words, we would like this diachronic exploration of the readings and interpretations of Lesya Ukrainka's work to also allow us to better understand the evolution of the status of women within the cultural field in the Ukrainian and Soviet world.

In fact, contrary to the emancipatory intentions of the Bolsheviks, any specially feminine thought movement (*i.e.* either made by women or concerned with women) ceased to exist in the Soviet world. Ukrainian women's organisations were banned on the grounds of “bourgeois nationalism”. The issue was only relevant in the USSR insofar as it was linked to the USSR's economic construction project and its family ideals (see on this subject, Kis, 2012; and Baker's *Gender in Twentieth-Century Eastern Europe and the USSR*, 2016 –, a collective volume whose contributors propose to study the instrumentalisation of women's discourse in the USSR), or to the maternal function (see Buckley, 1981, 1989). Certainly, the theoretical writings of Bebel (*The Woman and Socialism [Die Frau und der Sozialismus*, 1879]), Engels (*The Origin of the Family, Private Property and the State [Der Ursprung der Familie, des Privateigentums und des Staats*, 1884]), but also of Zetkin (*The Women's Workers' and Women's Question of the Present Day [Die Arbeiterinnen- und Frauenfrage der Gegenwart*, 1889]) and Kollontai (*The Social Foundations of the Women's Question [Социальные основы женского вопроса*, 1909]) caused a major revolution in consciousness by asserting the importance of economic independence as a prerequisite for female emancipation. However, for the Soviets, feminism and national identity did not always mix (or could only mix under Party control). Propaganda (see Chatterjee, 1999) used the image of women to call for union and work (in the factory or on the tractor – see Ilic, 2001). But the image and value of the woman still depended largely on her taking on household tasks, which determined whether she was a good or bad woman: the Romanian researcher Miroiu (2007) calls this “Room-Service Feminism”. For her, communism is in fact a state patriarchy, which may be debatable (see Studer, 2015). For other researchers, communist feminism is *a priori* a *contradictio in terminis* (see *Aspasia*, 2007).

Hence this question: if the readings of Ukrainka centered on the women's question that Ukrainian critics develop after 1991 bear the mark of their discovery of Western feminisms, aren't these readings also built against the Soviet conception of the women's cause? And to what extent do we still find, in the mode of reaction and not of conformity, traces of the influence of this Soviet doxa in the Ukrainian readings of Ukrainka after 1991?

2) *Ukrainian or Western(ist) readings of Ukrainka?*

This also raises the question: should we consider that the feminism developed by women intellectuals and writers in Ukraine after the fall of the USSR has liberated their speech as a typically Ukrainian feminism insofar as its expression was made possible by the “rebirth” of Ukraine as an independent nation, and by a new “Ukrainian-centered” (*i.e.* freed from Soviet imperatives) reading of founding texts such as those of Ukrainka? Or should we consider that it was the reopening to European and more broadly Western (thus also American) influences that caused a major upheaval in the history of interpretations of Ukrainka? Of course, we will not fall into the trap of essentialism, but we will study the construction of identities, traditions and even fantasized filiations, as well as mechanisms of intellectual and cultural transfers and exchanges.

It would seem that there is a clear gap between the Ukrainian feminism of which Ukrainka is the representative, and that which have developed in post-1991 Ukraine. The American historian Marta Bohachevsky-Chomiak (see 1988) considers that (despite the movements organised in Austro-Hungarian Galicia, such as the “Ruthenian Women’s Club”, created in Stanislav – now Ivano-Frankivsk – in 1884) if there is a feminism in Ukraine at the time of Ukrainka, it is an unconscious feminism; and she notes that this Ukrainian “feminism” is the means of the construction “a woman citizen” (see also Roudnitska, 1998). In other words, this Ukrainian-style “feminism” is, according to Bohachevsky-Chomiak, a feminism of action, not of ideology; consequently, none of the instituted shades of Western feminism (ranging from the most liberal to the most radical) corresponds entirely to the Ukrainian “feminist” values of the turn of the 20th century. However, the feminism of Ukrainka’s female readers in post-1991 Ukraine is an interpretive feminism largely inspired by Western women’s, gender and queer studies and marked by the readings and translations made by these Ukrainian critics (Pavlychko, Zborovska, Hundorova, Ageeva and others) of Western intellectuals (Simone de Beauvoir, Luce Irigaray, Hélène Cixous, Julia Kristeva, Kate Millett and Jean Paulette Bethke Elshstain), many of whom were not even frowned upon, but were invisible, inaccessible, because they were not translated, during the Soviet era. In other words, the readings of Ukrainka developed by these Ukrainian critics are backed by interpretative tools inspired by movements that practice what Ukrainka would have probably called a “feminine separatism”.

How do the critics we will study assume this not only ideological, but also geocultural gap? And do they not use it to create a typically Ukrainian feminism from the feminism they import from the West? These questions are all the more important for us, as (even if she believed that not all Western countries were equally advanced, since, in an article, entitled “New perspectives and old shadows. “The New Woman” of Western European Letters” [Ukrainka, 2021, vol. 7: 114], she notes that “the relationship to women in French literature has always lagged behind other literatures¹⁷”) Ukrainka herself was very open to European influences through her travels (in Bulgaria, Germany, Switzerland and even Egypt) and through her readings and translations (she was fluent in French, German, Italian, ancient Greek and Latin, not to mention the Slavic languages, Bulgarian, Polish, Russian and Ukrainian). And if it goes without saying that a culture, whatever it may be, is always nourished by its encounters with the other and the foreign, it is important to ask to what extent these European/Western influences (in Ukrainka’s work on the one hand, and in its interpretations by post-1991 Ukrainian critics on the other) undergo or do not undergo transformations that inscribe them in a temporality proper to the history of mentalities specific to the Ukraine. It would seem that the answer to this question is “yes”, since as early as 1991 Pavlychko published an article entitled “Does Ukrainian Literary Criticism Need a Feminist School?” In a gesture openly close to that of Ukrainka (who is one of the major authors of her corpus of study), she proposed a project of overcoming the provincial and peripheral assignment imposed on Ukrainian culture by both Russian and Ukrainian (male)

¹⁷ We translate: “отношение к женщине было всегда во французской литературе очень отсталым по сравнению с другими литературами.”

scholars, and to do so precisely by breaking away from the (quantitative) domination of patriarchal, post-imperial and post-Soviet ideology, and by giving specifically Ukrainian modernism and women's studies a place in the academic world equal to that of European literatures. Wanting to be ahead of the critics (and indeed she was derided by many male academics), Pavlychko immediately made it clear, in terms borrowed from Lesya Ukrainka, that this import into Ukrainian literary criticism of women's studies did not amount to an attempt to silence male voices, let alone an attempt at sedition – she was later to say: “It is necessary to write as much as possible about women in Ukrainian history, society, culture and about the existence [...] of a Ukrainian woman. It is not about particular female ambitions, it is not about revenge for unjust contempt, it is not about a call for female separatism” (Pavlychko, 2002: 26). Thus, there would be a “Ukrainian way” for women's studies – a way that Ukrainka would have helped to trace.

3) *A post-Soviet feminist reading of Ukrainka?*

The above questions are further complicated by the fact that post-1991 Ukrainian readings of Ukrainka place at the heart of the interpretative process of Ukrainka's works the question of the relationship between female emancipation and national¹⁸ emancipation. Hence the question: can these feminist readings of Ukrainka, which cannot be understood without taking into account the context of the fall of the USSR, really be constructed as typically Ukrainian, or are they not rather post-Soviet? The question is complex, because Ukrainka herself linked the two questions of female emancipation and national emancipation, and her work thus constitutes a model that allows critics who interpret her works after 1991 to “straddle” the USSR in order to claim a specifically Ukrainian filiation (on the way the anti-imperialist movement prefigures anti-Soviet and postcolonial Ukrainian comparatism, see Shkandrij, 2001).

The journal *Clio* devoted its fifty-third issue (2021) to the “Gender of independence” and to a comparison between the feminisms of the former colonies and empires of South America and colonial Africa. However, this method and perspective should also be applied to the countries of the former USSR. There are indeed traumas of Soviet origin which, although they are differentiated, are no less shared. Moreover, some critics (Solovey, 2018) have argued that if there is a feminism in the countries of the former USSR, it is only in the form of a copy of ‘Western’ feminism. In this way, there could be no specifically Ukrainian (or nationally Ukrainian) feminism, and the “identity feminism” specific to the emancipating countries of the former USSR would indeed be an Eastern European feminism, *i.e.* a feminism tending towards Europeaness. Graff (2003), on the other hand, argues that Ukrainian feminism can be considered “contradictory” or even “inconsistent” if studied according to the Western principle of “waves”, and not as Ukrainian (see also, for complementary approaches to the issue, Krassimira Daskalova, 2010, 2012; Tlostanova, 2010, 2011). If it is obvious that the reading grids developed by Western feminisms have profoundly influenced the evolution of interpretative gestures in Ukrainian academia since 1991, it seems to us that, in order to provide elements of an answer to the above questions, it is important to address the question of the corpora to which these grids are applied. For, if the interpretative grids influence the texts, the reciprocal is also true, and it therefore seems relevant to us to ask to what extent the corpus of study composed by the works of Ukrainka has been able to evolve the grids of reading of Western inspiration that have been applied to it after 1991.

¹⁸ It should be noted here that, according to Martha Bohachevsky-Chomiak, the term “nationalism” in this context should not be understood in its Western sense, but rather as a “patriotic nationalism” (see also Hrytsenko, 2022; and Brubaker, 1996).

4) *An intra-comparative approach of the interpretations of Ukrainka's works in Ukraine after 1991*

It is also important to ask whether the situation already described by Ukrainka – who noted, and regretted, that the ideology of Galician women writers was much more virulent than that which she herself considered typically Ukrainian – is reflected, *mutatis mutandis*, in the mapping of readings of Ukrainka's texts in post-1991 Ukraine. This question is all the more relevant because, although institutes and research centres for women's and gender studies have been created in Kyiv, Lviv, Odessa and Kharkiv between 1995 and 1999, there is (or was, as recent events may change the situation) a strong ideological disparity between these different centres of women's studies. To take just one example, it would seem that the gesture of linking the women's question to that of the possibility of inventing a national identity is practised more by researchers in the West and Centre of Ukraine than in the East. This could be explained by the factor of cultural exchanges (which are – or were – more active with Europe in the West, more active with Russia in the East) on the one hand, and that of migratory movements on the other, since part of the population of the western regions is the product of Russian immigration. For example, some scholars of women's studies in Kharkiv contrast national identity and feminism and emphasise the dependence of Ukrainian culture on the Russian Empire (on feminism in Russia, see Robertson, 2011; Kay, 2000). We will therefore propose an intra-comparative approach to the readings of Ukrainka's works proposed by Ukrainian critics over the last thirty years, asking whether there are interpretive specificities within the Ukrainian academic field linked to geo-cultural data.

To sum up, the aim of our project is to highlight the cultural aspects of the readings of Ukrainka's work, from her lifetime to nowadays. Or rather – for there can be no culture without intercultural intersections, to the point that interculturality seems to us to precede “culturality” – we would like to highlight the intercultural aspects of these readings, and to show how these readings are situated at the confluence of several currents in the history of ideas, some of which have their source in the Ukrainian world before 1917, others in the Western world of the same period, others in the Soviet world, others in the Western world of the 1970s, and others in the post-1991 Ukraine.

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